

ISic3656

I.Sicily inscription 3656

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

unknown

Material

limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2018.07.17 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

necropolis in contrada Pezzino

Coordinates

37.304555, 13.574498

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory AG S 156

Physical Description

Lower corner of a block of local yellow stone, intact below; possibly above, but broken on other sides.

Dimensions

Height 15 cm

Width 17 on left, 19 on right cm

Depth 16 cm

Layout

two engraved faces, each with two lines of large Greek letters

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. [---]

1. χα[---]

2. μα[---]

Apparatus**Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

EDR 139408

Bibliography

Dell'Orto, L., Franchi, R.1988. Veder greco: le necropoli di Agrigento : mostra internazionale, Agrigento, 2 maggio-31 luglio 1988. Rome. At 395 ph

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